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A PROJECT REPORT

DETERMINING SHEAR WAVE VELOCITY USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS:
A CASE STUDY IN SOUTH TANO FIELD.

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ABBREVIATIONS

MSE – Mean Squared Error

MLP – Multiple Layer Perceptron

SGD – Stochastic Gradient Descent

ReLU – Rectified Linear Unit

DSI – Dipole Sonic Imager

ANN – Artificial Neural Networks

ADAM – Adaptive Moment Estimation

SKLEARN – Scikit Learn

RMSE – Root Mean Square Error

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ABSTRACT

An important variable in the analysis of hydrocarbon reserves is shear wave velocity. But since there is no data on the shear wave velocity, it has become necessary to estimate this value using data from well logs. Using the petro-physical data that is readily available, numerous mathematical models are created to forecast this parameter. We first employed empirical relationships, multivariate regression, and artificial neural networks to forecast the shear wave velocity (V_s). A powerful technique called artificial neural networks make use of the correlation between the desired parameter and the information that is currently available. This technique allows us to pinpoint the variables that influence the shear wave velocity. Artificial neural networks are easy to train and provide a reliable shear wave velocity prediction model.

In order to determine how different well logs affect shear wave velocity after null and in appropriate petrophysical data has been processed and cleaned, this study used statistical approaches. Correlation is used in multiple regression to demonstrate how the shear wave velocity depends on the available log data. Strongly correlated data from the well logs were utilized to train, test, validate, and retrain the neural networks to forecast the shear wave velocity until a decreased root mean square error was obtained. The artificial neural network model achieved a root mean square error of 0.39. The closer the RMSE to zero, the better the prediction of a model.

As a result, we predicted shear wave velocity using compressional wave velocity from the sonic log. A new statistical strategy for predicting shear wave from wireline log data is described in this work. Shear wave velocity can be predicted using petrophysical parameters and any combination of compressional wave velocity, porosity, and density in sandstone formations. With a correlation coefficient of 0.87, the established approach can estimate shear wave velocity in sandstone formations.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 GENERAL INTRODUCTION

The complexity of hydrocarbon reservoirs is a significant challenge in the oil and gas industry. The absence of reliable information consequently leads to inappropriate predictions of reservoir parameters and hence a poor understanding of the reservoir behavior. In the past decade, physical models and other methods were enough to solve straightforward geological problems, but the same methods are inadequate to solve much more complex problems due to technological advancement. The existing techniques provide less satisfactory results and have a wider margin of error. Shear wave velocity estimation is an essential parameter due to its application in the evaluation of subsurface response to waves, soil improvement, and the surface structures' foundation strength. (Andisheh Alimoradi, 2011). Shear wave velocity is a parameter of enormous significance in exploratory studies in the oil and gas industry. However, due to the high cost of estimating it with classical methods, it has not been accounted for in most wells (Akhundi, Ghafoori, & Lashkariour, 2014).

Therefore, numerous methods and ways have been devised to estimate shear wave velocity with well-logging data from other wells (Yahua, Yin, Gao, & Zhao, 2019). Shear wave velocity is used to determine the lithology and geo-mechanical parameters such as the bulk and shear modulus and to predict the pore fluid. Different empirical relations have been developed to calculate the shear wave velocity, but these relationships are insufficient to provide adequate information about the shear wave. A better understanding of the mechanical properties of rock formations is essential during a hydrocarbon reservoir's development and production phases. Shear wave velocity logs help interpret seismic waves and identify bright spots.

However, data for shear wave logs are often not available and reliable. Data from standard well logs such as saturation and porosity are readily available. Dynamic tests such as compressional waves and geotechnical test measurements are available for all wells and correlations to provide a relationship between compressional waves and the shear wave velocity.

However, predictions for shear wave velocity can be made using compressional-wave velocity, lithology, saturation and porosity data with a precision of 9% and accuracy of 3%, respectively (M. L Greenberg, 1992). Empirical methods combine the various logs to predict the shear wave velocity and limitations such as efficiency, time factor and extensive technical know-how are steep curves for the predictions. Sophistication in technology has brought about advancement and new efficient ways that utilize computing power to make predictions for the shear wave velocity.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are computational models that have achieved promising results in dealing with complex phenomena. Predictions for reservoir parameters involve unrelated data due to lithological differences in reservoir parts. ANN receives input and attempts to identify patterns in data and generalizes a relationship among the data set (Chris Carpenter et al., 2021)

In this paper, artificial neural networks in combination with python programming language were utilized to create an efficient computational model that predicts shear wave velocity.

1.2 THE PROBLEM STATEMENT

Several well logs provide invaluable information on shear wave velocity through correlations. However, these methods are not entirely reliable for making accurate predictions for the shear wave velocity, and they are very costly since they require extensive technical know-how of varying well-logging methods (Shahoo, Moradzadeh, Ghavami, & Gholami, 2014). An improved method for accurately predicting the shear wave velocity using artificial neural networks will be employed to reduce the cost and time required to predict this essential parameter in exploring oil and gas. A backpropagation neural network is an efficient computational model for supervised learning. This neural network was used in prediction using data from well logs. A neural network with backpropagation in python programming language was used to estimate the shear wave velocity.

1.3 OBJECTIVES

1.3.1 MAIN OBJECTIVES

The main objective is to predict shear wave velocity from conventional well logs using strong relationships between the log and the shear wave velocity.

1.3.2 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- 1) To establish the relationship between the various well logs and the shear wave velocity.
- 2) To use artificial neural networks to predict the shear wave velocity based on the relationship.
- 3) To find the shear wave velocity using empirical correlations.
- 4) To compare values from both the ANN and the empirical methods.

1.4 JUSTIFICATION

Methods used to estimate the shear wave velocity can be categorized into; classical methods (empirical methods), theoretical methods and laboratory tests. These methods establish relationships among well logs and emphasize the relevance of using the information to predict the shear wave velocity from correlations. The other methods fail to provide accurate predictions of shear wave velocity compared to estimating it from the conventional well logs. Back-Propagation Neural Networks help provide the neurons' required outputs depending on the type of data provided to the input neurons.

1.5 THE GEOLOGY AND LOCATION OF THE SOUTH TANO FIELD

Ghana has four sedimentary basins: Accra Keta basin, Tano basin, Voltaian basin, and Saltpond basin.

However, the Tano basin has been of interest in oil and gas exploration and production. The Tano Basin and the St. Paul Fracture zone are bounded by the Saltpond basin in the Eastern and Western side respectively. The basin was formed during the trans-marginal movements that resulted in South America and Africa (Adda, 2013). Various rifting and subsidence processes during the Jurassic era birthed a deep basin. The geologic conditions at that time allowed for the deposition of shales. The South Tano Field can be found 60km from the coast of Ghana in the Tano Basin. The field has an expanse of about 175km² with reach of about 1300m to 1900m within water depths. The South Tano Petroleum Agreement was made between the Government of the Republic of Ghana and The Ghana National Petroleum Corporation, Exploration and Production Company Limited, Blue Star Exploration Ghana Limited, and Heritage Exploration and Production Ghana Limited on 18th July 2014 and became effective on the 5th February 2015.

The South Tano block is located within a known hydrocarbon deposit, according to field data. The South Tano License's major aim is the Turonian age Mahogany reservoirs that were successfully targeted in the Jubilee and TEN operations. Mahogany sands are constituted of amalgamated turbidities fan and channel complexes that were deposited in deep water slopes and basin settings. These reservoirs are known to have a distinct seismic response and can thus be identified using 3D seismic data, such as the dataset on the block.

The Mahogany-1 discovery well met sands with a gross thickness of 250m and a net thickness of 40-90m, with a porosity of 20% and a permeability of 100 millidarcy to 1000 millidarcy holding 37° API oil (Dailly et al., 2012). Wells drilled into the Mahogany reservoirs have produced up to 15,000-20,000 barrels of oil per day in offset fields and 8,000-15,000 barrels per day in development wells. (Peter Elliot et., 2019).

Figure 1: Location of the South Tano Field

Figure 2: The South Tano Block

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Scientists often do exploration for oil and gas reserves by sending energy through the earth's crust by way of waves and subsequently measuring the wave's reflection back to the surface. This extensive process requires vibrating trucks, explosives and air guns purposely made for use underwater. Seismic exploration refers to studying the earth using sound waves and making inferences based on the speed they travel through the crust. Seismology refers to the composition of layers of rocks on the earth, which impacts how wave energy interacts with underground materials. Intrinsic properties such as the rock type and porosity of the reservoir rocks affect the shear wave velocity. Conventionally, these properties are estimated from the petrophysical logs, with compression and shear sonic data being the primary input to the correlations.

2.1 SHEAR WAVE VELOCITY

A shear wave is a wave capable of travelling in material by moving perpendicular with the wave's direction. Shear causes the material to change shape while maintaining the volume. This is possible by the pair of force pulling the material in opposite directions. For an elastic medium, its original shape will be maintained after shear. The velocity (v) of a shear wave is equal to the square root of the ratio of shear modulus (G), a constant of the medium, to density (ρ) of the medium, $v = \sqrt{G/\rho}$ (Gregerson, 2019).

The shear wave velocity can be measured by rotating samples from well logs so that the incident wave reaches the interface with an angle of incidence, θ_i . Seismologists in the time past, used non-invasive methods in the prediction of the velocity of the subsurface. Seismic reflection methods, body-wave arrival times, surface-wave dispersion and free-oscillation periods of the earth are some of the methods used in the determination of the earth's structure (Boore, 2006)

In understanding the subsurface response to the waves, it is important to understand the effects of ground motion on the geology. This helps in determining the geologic features that affect the wave's propagation. The shear and compressional wave velocity, density and nonlinear properties of both soil and rock are some material properties of interest. These parameters of interest are

obtained from well logs, providing information that can be fine-tuned to estimate the shear wave velocity. (Boore, 2006)

An essential reason for predicting shear wave velocity in the oil and gas industry is to learn about the geological and geotechnical features of the reservoir. The shear wave velocity helps to detect anisotropy in the subsurface. (Akhundi, Ghafoori, & Lashkariour, 2014)

Shear wave splitting happens when a polarized shear wave interacts with a polarized anisotropic medium. The incident shear wave splits into two polarized shear waves. The optimal place to drill will be in the region with the highest degree of anisotropy since there will be the most fractures there. It is frequently used to test for the desired anisotropy. These measures enhance understanding of the density and orientation of the cracks and shed light on the degree of anisotropy. (Aki & Richards, 2002)

An incident shear wave may undergo a change in its known orientation or properties of the medium while exiting an isotropic medium. A polarized shear wave incident on a new anisotropic material, divides into two shear waves, one of which is faster and parallel to the crystals or fissures in the new medium. The time gap between the divided waves reveals the density of the cracks in the medium. The orientation of the rapid shear wave captures the direction of the medium cracks. In weakly anisotropic homogeneous media, the incident shear wave divides, and the difference in travel velocities between the two shear waves can be explained when comparison of their polarizations with the area and the dominant anisotropy direction is made. The interactions between the tiny particles that make up solids and liquids can be used as an analog for how waves travel through materials. (Vecsey & Babuska, 2008)

Solids are more quickly penetrated by waves than liquids are. Shear wave velocity can also be used to determine a medium's porosity because a faster shear wave indicates the rock matrix and a slower shear wave implies fluids. One of the many factors that affects how long it takes between shear wave arrivals is the anisotropy and porosity of the formation.

Media with wider, more substantial cracks will endure longer than media with smaller, more closed fissures. This has been used to efficiently map the high-pressure-induced fracture networks, which can be compared to how waves move through materials.

reservoir fracturing. Seismic waves moving through a material having aligned fissures initiate the entire process. Currently, this is the most effective way to learn about the fracture networks in a hydrocarbon reservoir. The best production in a field is associated with an area with multiple small fractures that are open allowing for constant flow of the hydrocarbons.

The shear wave velocity, V_s , depends on the following material properties:

$$V_s = \sqrt{\frac{G}{\rho}} \quad (2-1)$$

Where G is the shear modulus and ρ is the density of the material.

Figure 3: Direction of Movement of Waves Through the Earth.

2.2 PETROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES

The prediction of shear wave velocity depends on specific physical models of the rock. In the petroleum industry, it is a goal to determine the shear velocity using well logging tools.

Geomechanical parameters are fundamental in the oil and gas industry

The 'Xu-white model' predicts the shear wave velocity in the carbonate reservoir. The model (Xu & Payne, 2009) established that porosity and mineral content could be used to predict the shear wave velocity. The shear wave velocity of a saturated media can be calculated by the bulk modulus and shear modulus of the media and is expressed as;

$$v_s = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_{sat}}{\rho_{sat}}} \quad (2-2)$$

Compressional velocity, porosity, clay volume fraction, permeability, cementation exponent and other factors can be determined from an acoustic log, sonic and neutron logs, gamma-ray logs, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), and combinations of porosity and resistivity data, respectively.

Because of how complex the relationship between the Vs and other rock properties are, the only methods that provide information about the rock and fluid properties, well logs, is used in the prediction of the shear wave velocity.

2.2.1 SONIC LOG

Sonic logs are used to estimate the strength and static elastic moduli. (McNally, 1990).

Sonic logs provide essential information about ground motion. A type of sonic log, array sonic logs, provides invaluable information on petrophysical properties. Array sonic logs provide information about numerous acoustic properties such as the formation's permeability, porosity, acoustic impedance and elastic properties. Depending upon the type of sonic log, it can possess a monopole or a dipole source. A formation where its measured compressional wave velocity in the borehole fluid is greater than the encompassing shear wave velocity is a slow formation. Higher shear wave velocities than compressional wave velocities is a characteristic of a fast formation. The array sonic log having the monopole source is used the measurement of the Stoneley

compressional wave velocities used to estimate shear wave velocities in slow formations. The dipole source measures similar properties with greater accuracy and consistency in slow and fast formations. (Crain E. R., 2004)

Figure 4: Source https://wiki.seg.org/wiki/Sonic_log

The measurements can be done with a sonde, freely suspended in the water contained in the borehole. The significant parts of the sonde are the source, receivers, and filter tube. (Shiyu Xu, 1996)

The sonic log measures how sound travels through rock, providing information on porosity. It also determines which fluid (a liquid or a gas) occupies the pore spaces. The velocity of the elastic wave through the media is expressed as a function of porosity as:

$$\phi_s = \frac{\Delta t_{log} - \Delta t_{matrix}}{\Delta t_{fluid} - \Delta t_{matrix}} \quad (2-2)$$

2.2.2 GAMMA RAY LOG

The radioactivity of a formation is measured using the gamma ray log by the measuring the gamma rays' weight concentrations (Potassium, Uranium and Thorium.) after scattering. It is expressed as

$$GR = \frac{\sum \rho_i v_i}{\rho_b} \quad (2-3)$$

Where:

ρ_i is the initial density of the radioactive material, and v_i is the bulk volume of the radioactive material. Whereas ρ_b is the formation density.

The shale volume can be calculated by calculating the gamma-ray index, I_{GR} , expressed as:

$$I_{GR} = \frac{GR_{log} - GR_{min}}{GR_{max} - GR_{min}} \quad (2-4)$$

2.2.3 NEUTRON LOG

The neutron log determines the formation hydrogen index, measured by a neutron tool. The tool sends radiation into the rock. These radiations collide with the nuclei in the formation and lose energy. The energy lost is relative to the mass of the nucleus with which the neutron collides. The porosity is determined by the index of neutrons that return. Shear and compressional wave velocity can be expressed from the neutron log as:

$$\frac{1}{v} = \frac{\emptyset}{v_f} + \frac{1-\emptyset}{v_m} \quad (2-6)$$

Where \emptyset is the porosity from the neutron tool, v_f and v_m are the fluid and rock matrix velocities, respectively.

2.2.4 FORMATION DENSITY LOG

The density log measures porosity by sending gamma rays into the formation. The rays undergo multiple collisions with the electrons in the rock, and some return to the surface, which is recorded by detectors. The returning gamma rays are measured at two different energy levels:

A higher energy level determines the bulk density and, therefore, the porosity and

A low-energy gamma-ray is used to determine the lithology of the formation.

The density log relates to porosity by the expression:

$$\phi = \frac{\rho_{matrix} - \rho_b}{\rho_{matrix} - \rho_f} \quad (2-5)$$

Where ρ_{matrix} is the density of the matrix, ρ_b is the bulk density, and ρ_f is the density of the fluid.

2.2.5 RESISTIVITY LOG

The resistivity logs are electrical logs that measure the resistivity of the formation. The borehole environment comprises the uninvaded zone, where the log measures the true resistivity of the formation, the invaded zone and the flushed zone. Archie's equation relates to the porosity, oil saturation, limestone water saturation, and sandstone reservoir. The bulk resistivity of a rock (R_o) saturated with an aqueous fluid of resistivity (R_w) is directly proportional to the resistivity of the fluid. ($R_o = FR_w$)

The F is called the formation factor, and it describes the effect of the pressure of the rock matrix. Where m is the cementation factor, a is the tortuosity index, and n is the saturation exponent, Archie's equations are given by:

$$R_o = aR_w\phi^{-m} \quad (2-8)$$

$$R_t = \frac{R_o}{\phi^2 S_w^{-n}} \quad (2-6)$$

2.3 ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS(ANN)

Neural networks refer to parallel computing devices attempting to model the brain's workings.

They reflect the behavior of the human brain by recognizing patterns. This model incorporates systems that enable the computations of tasks to be more efficient than the classical, traditional methods. Pattern recognition, optimization, and approximations are a few capabilities neural networks possess.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are task-efficient computing models that mimic how biological neural neurons send signals. ANN requires a vast collection of interconnected units with peculiar patterns that allow communication among all units. These units, called nodes or neurons, are processors which operate in parallel. All neurons are connected universally through a recognizable pattern. Neural networks depend mainly on data for training to learn by recognizing similar features and improving on their accuracy with time. ANN are computational models consisting of many units that processes received inputs and deliver outputs based on a certain defined activation function. The output signals are produced when the signals are combined with the activation function. Once the algorithms become fine-tuned, they become indispensable for high-speed and accurate data predictions. The interconnection of the neurons creates a connection link. The connection link is associated with a weight that has an input signal. Artificial neural networks (ANNs) are computational models which imitates the human brain in terms of understanding and cognition. ANNs are parallel adaptive algorithms hence needs training. Backpropagation is a powerful supervised learning method that was developed in the 1940s. Backpropagation algorithms provide a faster learning rate, giving powerful insights into how the change of weights and biases affects the overall behavior of the network. (Nielsen, 2019)

2.3.1 STRUCTURE OF ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK

The neural network structure comprises of artificial neurons connected intermittently with each other. They are simple processors processing received information while recognizing some simple features and passing it on to other neurons (Andisheh Alimoradi, 2011). The input layer, middle layer and output layer are the three layers that an artificial neural network comprises. The input layer takes data and sends it for transformation in the middle layer. The middle layer is responsible for analyzing the data and sending it to the output layer to further break down the data into a more

understandable form after processing. The network uses a rectified linear activation function to transfer data from the input layer to the middle layer. An artificial neural network accepts data input and is trained to predict further data. It is essential to allow the computational model to perform tasks efficiently. The network is provided with input data and the corresponding output. This process is also termed learning. The network is continuously fed with input data sets and their corresponding outputs, enabling it to learn the related patterns and assign various weights to each input parameter provided. The effects the input data may fail to account for is called bias. This layer, however, is not linked to all the primary neurons. Networks with one or more hidden layers are called forward feed networks linked to the output layers. The network uses a Levenberg-Marquardt learning rule to modify the weights assigned to the neurons by efficient and continuous looping of functions to obtain the best relationship between the input data and the outputs (Kumaraswamy, 2020). The weights and biases are essential concepts of neural networks.

Figure 5: The general structure of an ANN.

The building blocks of neural networks are vectors, linear regression and layers.

An ANN has several advantages, but one of the most recognized is that it can learn from observing data sets. In this way, ANN is used as a random function approximation tool. These tools help

estimate the most cost-effective and ideal methods for arriving at solutions while defining computing functions or distributions.

ANN takes data samples rather than entire data sets to arrive at solutions, saving time and money. ANNs are considered relatively simple mathematical models to enhance existing data analysis technologies. ANN are systems that learn to make predictions by following steps:

- a) ANN is fed with input data.
- b) The neural network then proceeds to make predictions.
- c) The prediction is compared to the desired output, otherwise known as the target.
- d) Adjustments are made to the neural networks to reduce the error in the prediction until desirable results are reached.

2.3.2 MINIMIZATION OF ERROR IN THE ANN THROUGH TRAINING

The weights and bias are possibly the most crucial concept of neural networks. The term loss refers to the error in the prediction made by neural networks. Therefore, a loss function is interpreted as a function that calculates the loss for a specific prediction. There is a need for the loss function to optimize the model to learn and decide which steps it should take to minimize the error. The loss function calculates the loss for a single data point, and the cost function calculates the loss for the entire dataset. Therefore, the cost of a neural network refers to the summation of all losses on the individual training samples. Some of the most commonly used loss functions allow the signals to propagate back into the network through the output layer.

Weights are adjusted using mathematical correlations that minimize the squared errors' sum.

Weights are calculated by minimizing the difference among network outputs after propagation.

Mathematically,

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N (\mathbf{y}_i - \mathbf{y}_i)^2 \quad (2-7)$$

where N refers to the number of samples, and J is the network error for a single training iteration. The cost is a function of the sample data and the weights on the synapses. Error minimization can be effectively achieved by changing the weights since it is the parameter we can control. Training

of the neural network continues until the difference between the prediction and the desired target becomes minimal. Two problems may be encountered during the neural network training: overfitting and underfitting. Underfitting occurs when the ANN model fails to capture the data's dependencies because of the model's simplicity, leading to poor generalization capability upon the addition of new data sets. On the other hand, overfitting occurs when the model learns the existing data too well and easily captures the dependencies among the existing data.

2.3.3 GENERALIZED DELTA RULE

The generalized delta rule determines how to update a neural network during a backpropagation data training step. It is a mathematically derived formula that is derived in the cause of attempting to reduce error in the output of a neural network through Stochastic Gradient Descent. Gradient descent is an optimization algorithm commonly used to train neural networks. However, the Adaptive Moment Estimation (ADAM) solver is an algorithm for optimization. It is an efficient method that works with large datasets involving many parameters. ADAM solver was chosen to build the model because it requires less memory and is efficient. Training data aids the models in learning over time, and the cost function acts as a gauge for accuracy over each iteration. Gradient descent is applied to the ANN to find the direction and rate at which the network parameters should be updated. The way to measure the error is called the cost function and the mean squared error (MSE) is used to compute errors. MSE measures the amount of error in statistical models. The MSE measures the average squared difference between predicted and target values. The direction to move to reduce the error is known by taking the derivative of the MSE. Squaring the difference between the estimated value and the target eliminates negative values, thus ensuring that the error is always greater than zero or equal to zero. Additionally, taking the square of the error increases the more significant errors and this disproportionality demonstrates the influence of larger values in producing more significant errors.

Figure 6: Illustration of the influence of closeness of data points in regression.

The closer the data point is to the regression line, the lesser the error, subsequently a decreasing MSE. Mathematically,

$$MSE = \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y})^2}{n} \quad (2-8)$$

Where:

y_i represents the i^{th} observed value.

\hat{y}_i is the corresponding estimated value.

n = number of observations.

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is a standard way to measure the error of a model in predicting quantitative data.

Mathematically, it is denoted as:

$$RMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}}{n} \quad (2-12)$$

where:

n denotes the number of observations

y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n denotes observed values

$\hat{y}_1, \hat{y}_2, \dots, \hat{y}_n$ denotes predicted values

CHAPTER 3

3.1 METHODOLOGY

- Microsoft Excel was used to display the data sets and generate graphs of all the well logs against the shear wave velocity data.
- Inconsistent or null values were deleted and refilled through interpolation.
In this work, we have used the (Castagna, 1985) models to estimate the shear velocities. Laboratory ultrasonic data and in situ data measurements provided reliable results when superimposed according to the model.

3.1.0 DATA COLLECTION AND PREPARATION

The compressional wave velocities were determined from the sonic interval transit time for the data sets for the formation. The geology of the South Tano Field indicates the dominance of sandstone formation. The compressional wave velocities were generated from the relation;

$$Vp = \frac{l}{\Delta ITT} \quad (3-1)$$

Shear wave velocity is a function of compressional wave velocity, but compressional wave velocity is not necessarily a function of shear wave velocity.

The compressional wave velocity data is then used in (Castagna, 1985) empirical equation;

$$[Vs = 0.80416 * Vp - 0.85588] \quad (3-2)$$

to generate the shear wave velocity data.

(Castagna, 1985) equation or the mud rock line relation is a linear relation between seismic Pwave and S-wave.

3.2. DERIVATION OF SHEAR WAVE VELOCITY DATA

(Castagna, 1985) predicted the relationship between the compressional and shear wave velocity for both sandstones and shales from shear-compressional velocity plot gotten from in situ data as given in the following relations:

$$V_s = (0.8621 * V_p) - 1.1724 \quad (3-3)$$

However, (Castagna, 1985) suggested that if the lithology is well known, researchers can fine-tune a slight difference between shear wave velocity predicted from compressional wave velocity for sandstone, shale, dolomite and limestone formations through the use of regression of superimposed laboratory ultrasonic and in situ data. These expressions are presented below;

$$V_s = (0.80416 * V_p) - 0.85588 \quad (\text{Sand beds}) \quad (3-4)$$

$$V_s = (0.76969 * V_p) - 0.86735 \quad (\text{Shale beds}) \quad (3-5)$$

$$V_s = -(0.58321 * V_p) - 0.07775 \quad (\text{Dolomite}) \quad (3-6)$$

$$V_s = -(0.05508 * V_p^2) + (1.01677 * V_p) - 1.03049 \quad (\text{Limestone}) \quad (3-7)$$

The dominant formation for the South Tano Field is sandstone so the equation for sand beds was used to generate the shear wave velocities.

3.3 DESIGN OF NEURAL NETWORK

ANN networks using the backpropagation neural networks model (BPNN) with Python is shown in the diagram below:

Figure 7: Illustration of the structure of ANN

The data set was loaded into the pandas' data frame, pandas is a python library and invalid data was cleaned.

Initially, the network is constructed using 80% of the dataset to test and train the network for further learning.

3.4 LINEAR REGRESSION

Regression is a statistical method used to estimate the strength of the relationship between a dependent and independent variable. Linear regression uses the least-squares method to determine the line of best fit. The least-squares method minimizes the sum of squares created by a mathematical function (Brian, 2022).

A heat map is a graphical representation of two-dimensional data. Data values are represented in a matrix with unique colorations. Python programming and its data visualization library called seaborn were used to generate the heat map. Heat maps are relevant because they help visualize the data's correlation matrix for feature selection to make better predictions. It is used to find the relationship between multiple features and which features are best for building models to make predictions.

Figure 8: Python programming seaborn heatmap indicating the correlation of multiple features.

Correlation coefficients of positive 0.4 to 1.0 and negative coefficients of -0.4 to -1.0 were deemed the better parameters to build the model.

A linear relation was obtained for the correlation of RHOB, NPFI, GR, LLD, LLS and shear wave velocity. The linear relation is as follows;

$$Vs = m(RHOB + NPHI + GR + LLD + LLS) + C \quad (3-8)$$

Where Vs = shear wave velocity;

m = gradient;

C = intercept.

The equations for the linear regression of the several parameters against shear wave velocity have been displayed on the various graphs.

- The python package NumPy was imported and class LinearRegression was also imported from sklearn model to correlate the parameters.

3.5 MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION

Multiple regression analysis uses correlations among several well-log data to estimate the target variable. For any parameter to be estimated, it is initially communicated to several other parameters. An advantage of multiple regression over simple linear regression is that it is more accurate since it has embedded capabilities to summarize more information. In order to use this method, it is advisable to choose data that is independent of each other and hence have low correlations. Inferred from empirical studies, the selection of dependent variables has been explicitly explained, although predictions should be presented for each newly discovered field. In order to determine the input parameters, correlation coefficients for the several well logs should be determined by shear wave velocity data. The shear wave velocity was predicted using the data from well logs such as depth, the neutron porosity logs, bulk density, gamma ray and resistivity logs. Relationships among the parameters and shear wave velocity data were grouped into having positive or negative relations. The higher the coefficient of correlation (R^2) value, the better the strength of the relationship between shear wave velocity and the parameter. This was done using Python and the sklearn model. The parameters with high correlation coefficients were selected as input parameters.

- Multiple regression was implemented using three functions defined in the sklearn module in Python. They are the LinearRegression() function, the fit() method and the predict() method
- The LinearRegression() function creates a multiple regression model with 80% of the dataset for training.
- The fit() method is then used to train the linear regression model. It takes independent input parameters of the dataset and dependent variables (target variable) as the second input argument and after execution, it returns a trained linear regression model.
- The predict() method is used to predict values of the shear wave velocity for the remaining 20% of the dataset, which is the test data.
- The model's prediction yielded a root mean square error of 0.44, which can be interpreted as average. The closer the value is to zero, the better the prediction.

A multivariate model of the data solves for unknown coefficients $a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_5$

$$Vs = a_0 + a_1NPHI + a_2RHOB + a_3GR + a_4LLD + a_5LLS \quad (3-9)$$

Where a_0 is the intercept and a_1, a_2, a_3 ...are the coefficients of the input data.

$$Vs = [10.00002792117926] - 1.06802737e + 01 * NPHI - 4.36057640e - 01 * RHOB + 1.03812566e - 02 * GR + 1.28998012e - 02 * LLD + 2.30548082e - 01 * LLS \dots\dots\dots (3-10)$$

The model for the shear wave velocity. This model can be used for other fields where well log data for RHOB, NPHI, GR, LLD and LLS are known.

The regression and empirical equations methods are generally acceptable for estimating shear wave velocity for different lithologies. However, the regression method generally is more accurate than the method of the equation. Considering the limitations of these methods, other methods that can overcome these shortcomings are therefore necessary to estimate shear wave velocity to a greater

degree of accuracy. Therefore, a more powerful technique was suggested: the implementation of smart techniques such as artificial neural networks, which have achieved great success.

3.6 ANN

Artificial neural networks are parallel processing systems that detect extremely complex datasets patterns. They can have learning, training and remembering ability as well as the ability to generalize results. For this study, available data initially prepared, deemed as inappropriate data were omitted because they had a negative effect on network training and testing. A multi-layer feedforward neural network was used to build the model. The network comprised neurons and layers. The layers are responsible for designated tasks. The middle layer, otherwise called the hidden layer, analyses information entered from the input layer. Analyzed data is sent from the hidden layer, converted into meaningful forms by the output layer, and returned to the environment.

- The ANN model was implemented using three functions defined in the sklearn module in Python. The functions are the Multiple Layer Perceptron Regressor, `MLPRegressor()` function, the `fit()` method and the `predict()` method. The MLP Regressor was selected because it handles multiple input parameters and layers.
- The `MLPRegressor()` function is used to create an ANN model with 80% of the dataset for training.
- An Activation function is a function added to an artificial neural network to enable it to learn complex patterns in datasets. An activation function is vital because of its ability to add non-linearity in neural networks and to act as a threshold factor.
- Rectified Linear Unit, ReLU, as an activation function was used. ReLU gives output between 0 and 1 (Noriega, 2005) based on the criteria; $g(z) = \max(0, z)$ such that

$$\bullet \quad g(z) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } z < 0 \\ z & \text{if } z \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3-2)$$

- ReLU serves as the transfer function from the input layer to the hidden layer.
- This model used the Adaptive Moment Estimation (ADAM) algorithm solver as the optimization technique. ADAM is a stochastic gradient-based optimizer minimizing the

cost function (Kingma & Ba, 2015). It minimizes the error between the actual and predicted values faster, hence its use in the model.

- Hidden layers in ANN are layers between the algorithm's input and output layers, in which the function applies weights to the inputs and directs them through an activation function. The number of neurons in the hidden layer was determined through trial and error. Accordingly, the best-selected model network with the highest correlation coefficient and lowest error has eight neurons in its hidden layer according to this work.
- The fit() method is then used to train the MLP model. It takes independent input parameters of the dataset and dependent variables (target variable) as the second input argument and after execution, it returns a trained MLP regression model.
- The predict() method is used to predict values of the shear wave velocity for the remaining 20% of the dataset, which is the test data.

Other different training algorithms and transfer functions were tried in the design of the ANN model in order to get a desirable network. It was established that a multi-layered feed-forward network with an error backpropagation algorithm in estimating the geomechanical parameters give the most preferred result.

This study used several input parameters with various hidden neurons to predict the shear wave velocity. Input parameters with the smallest margin of error and high correlation coefficient were chosen as the desirable inputs for the networks. The input parameters that returned the best results belonged to a network of five (GR, NPHI, RHOB, LLD and LLS) with eight neurons in the hidden layer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. APPROPRIATE DATA SELECTION

This study's core samples are from depths of 1520m to 3635.6m. The petrophysical parameters that directly influence shear wave velocity were ascertained. Multiple regression and the Artificial Neural Network were developed based on the correlations. The ANN was based on the back propagation neural network with hidden layers.

Both the neural network and the multiple regression method gave promising outcomes. Coefficient of correlation is a statistical measure of the degree to which changes to a one variable predicts changes in another variable. In positive correlations, the values of the two values increases or decreases in tandem whereas in negative correlations, as the value of one variable increases the other decreases and vice versa.

Coefficient of correlations are expressed as values between +1 and -1. A coefficient of correlation of +1 indicates perfect relationship between the variables as changes occur in the same direction. Likewise, a negative correlation means the values of one variable predicts a change in the opposite direction. A correlation coefficient of zero indicates no discernable relationship between the shear wave velocity and the variable of interest.

The coefficient of correlation determines the strength of the relationship between variables and it is denoted as R. However, the coefficient of determination, denoted as R^2 , is the square of the coefficient of correlation.

The coefficient of determination gives an idea on how many data points fall within the results of the line formed by the regression equation. The higher the coefficient, the higher the percentage of data points the plot passes through and consequently, the better the fit.

4.1.1 LINEAR GRAPHS DISPLAYING COEFFICIENT OF DETERMINATION (R^2)

Figure 9: A graph of predicted Vs. against actual Vs

A graph indicating a plot of actual values for shear wave velocity against predicted values of the shear wave velocity. The model had a coefficient of correlation of 0.84 which confirms the returned good results.

Figure 10: Plot of Actual Vs. Predicted MLP

A graph showing a plot of actual shear wave velocity values as against the predicted shear wave values. The coefficient of correlation for the graph is 0.87. This means the model achieved a test score of 87%.

Figure 1: Vs against RHOB

A graph of the shear wave velocity against RHOB which returned a positive coefficient of correlation of 0.48.

Plots of the shear wave velocity data against other well log parameters are displayed below: The coefficient of determination for each of the plots have been indicated on it.

Figure 2: Vs against NPHI

Figure 3: Plot of Vs against GR

Figure 4: Vs versus LLS

However, the relationship between the shear wave velocity and both the LLS and LLD is strong for smaller values. This explains why the outliers are in regions of high LLS and LLD values. The model will attain a poor accuracy and a lower coefficient of determination if all the LLS and LLD values were significantly higher values. Nonetheless, for the given datasets, the LLD and LLS recorded from well logging returned good coefficient of determination values hence the inclusion as input parameters.

Figure 5: Vs versus LLD

4.1.2 FITTING OF GRAPHS USING OTHER METHODS TO COMPARE BEST FITS.

The relationship between the shear wave velocity and the well logs was also fitted using other relationships such as logarithmic, power and exponential graphs. However, the algorithms that were used to build the model have been designed such that it uses all possible forms of the relationships between the shear wave velocity and the variable well log data and fits the model with the best possible relationship.

Figure 6: Polynomial graph of Vs Versus GR

Figure 7: Exponential graph of Vs against GR

Figure 8: Logarithmic graph of Vs against GR

Figure 9: Exponential graph of Vs against RHOB

Figure 10: Exponential graph of Vs against RHOB

4.1.3 SELECTION OF INPUT PARAMETERS

In building the ANN model, the choice of input parameters for the model was based on how strongly the parameters correlated with the shear wave velocity. The linear regression helped to achieve this. The coefficient of determination (R^2) for the correlations was the reason for the selection of parameters. Higher positive correlations between 0.4 to 1.0 and negative correlations of -4.0 to -1.0 of the parameters against shear wave velocity were chosen as inputs. Low-value correlation coefficients contribute to better predictions, and very high correlation coefficients contribute to overfitting data sets.

Based the linear regression graph extending from figure 11 to 15, the bulk density log, the gamma ray, neutron-density log, the deep and shallow resistivity logs. The gamma ray giving a lower R-squared value among the rest of the parameters but still chosen was to check for overfitting and to ensure a robust ANN model.

In an attempt to checking whether the R-squared values can be improved, the various graphs of the shear wave velocity against the input parameters were plotted. Comparatively the same R-squared values were obtained.

4.2 PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

To assess the performance of the model, the score performance of the model evaluated the validity of the model based on the R-squared. The train score and test score give assessment to the model's performance based on its ability to predict the actual values of the shear wave velocity. Having a train score and a test score been the same value signifies a better model. The better the test or train score to 100, the better the model.

The multiple regression model gave a score of 84% for both its train and test data cases.

The ANN model achieved a score of 87% for both the trained dataset and tested datasets. Compared to multiple linear regression, the result demonstrates the high ability of artificial neural networks to predict geomechanical parameters. This further goes to show the ANN's superiority to the multiple regression.

4.3 ERROR ANALYSIS

With a trained and tested model ready, it is important to check how accurate the model is performing in predicting the actual values by measuring the error margin between the actual and predicted values. As discussed in the methodology, the error in the model was measured using the root mean square error (RMSE).

The multiple regression model with the selected input parameters gave a RMSE value of 0.44 while the ANN model gave a RMSE value of 0.39 after training to get a better performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSIONS

Shear wave velocity is estimated using empirical relationships that are based on several lithologies and a few petrophysical factors, including porosity and compressional wave velocity. Castagna's relation was applied in the current work to estimate the V_s . There is an input parameter for this relation (V_p). When a complete set of well logging data is not available, it is suggested to apply Castagna's relation, and its results are often satisfactory.

Shear wave velocity was predicted with an 87% correlation coefficient using artificial neural networks particularly the MLP, with the model's input parameters being gamma ray, the neutron porosity, bulk density, deep and shallow resistivity. The MLP technique was successful in estimating the V_s with a satisfactory error value, RMSE.

According to the coefficient of determination, artificial neural networks were the most effective way for estimating shear wave velocity among the different techniques employed to do so for the South Tano Basin. The ANN is the best way to predict the shear wave velocity with well logs as the hidden layers can be varied until a satisfactory prediction is made.

Since the model was trained with the target V_s values calculated from the empirical Castagna's equation, all its assumptions apply to the model.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Using values obtained from the Dipole Sonic Imager to train the model during the training of data sets even if the data were from other wells within the same basin, would have given a robust model with better predictions. The training and testing were done and compared to values obtained from empirical correlation (Castagna's equation). This indicates assumptions in the empirical equations are automatically factored in the ANN model. The use of DSI tool to directly fetch data for shear wave velocity will greatly improve the accuracy of the shear wave velocity prediction.

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